

The use of Kahoot! to promote Active Learning in Port Management and Operation subject in Civil Engineering degree

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Abstract

Port Management and Operation subject in Civil Engineering degree of the University of Alicante is a mainly theoretical subject, full of complex engineering terms. In addition, the schedule of this course is from 15 to 17 h, just after lunchtime. This causes a decrease in the attendance and motivation of the students throughout the course. To mitigate this problem, an Active Learning methodology was proposed. Personal response systems are mechanisms with a system of controls that, in real time, can be used to carry out questionnaires and interpret the results. One of these systems is the platform Kahoot!. The materials of each lesson were provided to the students so that they could work on the contents before the sessions (flipped classroom). A quiz is completed before and after each session to determine the degree of involvement of the students and the level of attention during the session. The first and last 5-10 minutes of each of the theory sessions were dedicated to the Kahoot! quizzes. Most of the students' connections were made with their mobile phones. The results show that the level of student engagement increases over the course, as the percentage of correct answers before the explanation increases over the course. It is also observed that after the lessons, the rate of correct answers increases, which indicates that the students are more involved and follow the class with greater interest than previously. Moreover, gamification improves the classroom learning atmosphere. The use of Kahoot! to promote active learning, to reinforce the knowledge of the concepts seen in class and to create an evaluative test in the form of a game were evaluated in a very positive way.

Keywords: Active Learning; Civil Engineering Education; Kahoot!; Soft Skills.

1 Introduction

Teaching in Spanish faculties generally involves a large number of students, whose active participation in classes and evaluation involves great difficulties (Pérez-Colodrero, 2020). Thus, one of the main problems in university teaching nowadays is the lack of motivation and participation on the part of the students (Pintor et al., 2014). The subject of Management and Operation of Ports of the Degree in Civil Engineering at the University of Alicante, although it has few students, there is a lack of motivation among them.

At the beginning of the 21st century, the first personal response systems appeared to alleviate this problem. These were initially called "clickers", which are mechanisms with a system of controls that, in real time, can be used to perform questionnaires and interpret the results (Pintor et al., 2014). One of these systems is Kahoot! platform. This platform is a personal or group response system that, based on the game, transforms the teaching-learning process (da Silva et al., 2018). In this way, students learn from a playful perspective (Jaber et al., 2016), their motivation, commitment and active participation are fostered (Sharples, 2000; Wang, 2015) and, at the same time, digital competence is developed (Álvarez-Rosa et al., 2018).

The recreational component of these games promotes student motivation, confirming the existence of a relationship between gamification and motivation (Kenny & McDaniel, 2011). Therefore, if one of the main objectives is to increase the motivation of students to achieve meaningful learning (Curto Prieto et al., 2019), games present a good opportunity to increase the motivation, desire and commitment of students in their teaching-learning process (Serrano et al., 2011).

Some educators consider game-based learning an effective method because it maintains the purpose of education, enhances player skill, and can be used in real life (Von Wangenheim & Shull, 2009). In fact, gamification has increased exponentially in education since 2014 perhaps because educational games put the learner at the centre of learning, which facilitates more fruitful and interesting learning (Torres-Toukourmidis et al., 2019). Therefore, the introduction of games in class aims to foster dynamism, engagement and motivation

among other factors (Lee & Hammer, 2011). But the current educational landscape demands the inclusion of technological advances to improve the quality and the learning process, which would be in line with the preferences of the millennial generation for more active and technological (Jain & Dutta, 2019).

Considering the benefits described above, this methodology has been implemented in the course of Port Management and Operation of the Degree in Civil Engineering at the University of Alicante to achieve the results obtained in similar studies in the scientific literature described for this resource. Thus, it is expected to improve the participation, performance and motivation of students in the subject, mainly in the theoretical part of it.

2 Method

This project was conducted within the framework of the course "Management and Operation of Ports" of the Civil Engineering Degree of the University of Alicante. This compulsory course is part of the fourth year of the degree within the branch of Transport and Urban Services. It is a subject that consists of 1.20 credits of theory, 0.60 credits of problems and 0.60 credits of fieldwork. The inclusion of the Kahoot platform was implemented in the 2018-2019, 2019-2020 and 2020-2021 courses of the subject of Port Management and Operation of the fourth year of the Degree in Civil Engineering at the University of Alicante. The experience evaluated a total of 14 students (6 in 2018-19, 4 in 2019-20 and 4 in 2020-21) during the theory hours shared between two professors every Wednesday of the second term from 15:00 to 17:00.

In this research, the Kahoot! platform was used to evaluate the level of attention, understanding and involvement of the students, both in their work at home and during the theoretical classes. This platform allows for questionnaires that can be answered individually or in groups, and also allows setting a time limit for answering the question. Students earn points for each correct answer as well as for the speed with which they answer the different questions correctly. For students to participate in the surveys, they must have a device connected to the network. It is not necessary to have an account on the platform application, simply know the test code and indicate a name or "nickname" to identify yourself during the duration of the questionnaire. When the time to answer each question is over or when all the participants have answered, the answer selected by each contestant, the correct answer, the score obtained in that question by each participant and the positions in the ranking are displayed. Finally, at the end of the questionnaire, it is possible to include questions to obtain feedback on the feelings of the students.

In our case, the tests were set to be answered individually by each of the students. Each test had a different number of questions depending on the length and complexity of the unit. The response time was set at 20 seconds for all cases. To determine the degree of enjoyment of the students in taking these tests, four questions were established only in the last test that was taken. The questions indicated the level of enjoyment valued between zero and five, the belief of having learned with the method (yes or no), the possible recommendation of the method (yes or no), and the level of satisfaction with the methodology, with the possibility of answering between zero to five.

On the first day of class, the procedure and teaching methodology that would be used during the theoretical classes of the course was explained. It was indicated that during each session two questionnaires would be conducted on the Kahoot! platform, one at the beginning and one at the end of the session. During this first class, a first test was carried out to find out the knowledge that the students had about the subject.

Throughout the following sessions, the first and last 5-10 minutes of each theoretical class were reserved for the completion of the questionnaires with the Kahoot! platform. This is because in each class two questionnaires were carried out with two purposes.

1) Before the theoretical explanation (BTE Test). Before the explanation of each lecture, a test was conducted with questions related to the topic. This made it possible to know the level of knowledge of the subject of the students, as well as their work at home and involvement with the subject since at the beginning of the course the theoretical development of each of the topics and their organization and distribution throughout the course were given.

2) After the theoretical explanation (ATE Test). After the explanation of the topics corresponding to each session, a test was conducted with repeated questions from the initial test and other new questions, but all of them related to the topic of the session. The purpose of this test is to determine the level of attention, motivation and learning of the students throughout the class.

Once all the students had answered each of the ATE test questions, the answers chosen by each one were commented on and discussed, and the correct answer was reasoned. At the end, the teacher of the session kept the results obtained by the participants in each session.

Finally, during the last session, the initial test (conducted on the first day) was repeated to see the increase in knowledge of the students concerning the beginning of the course.

3 Results

The first result to be analyzed is the results obtained by the students after the inverted class, that is, the previous evaluation of the knowledge of the students before the explanation of the unit in class. It should be born in mind that the students had all the information on the subject from the beginning of the course. Figure 1 shows the average results obtained by each of the courses evaluated for each of the 14 theoretical class sessions. As can be observed, in general, the percentage of correct answers before the theoretical explanation is between 54% and 71%, with an average of 61.6% in the three courses. Unit 10 stands out for its low percentage of correct answers, with an average of 45.7% in the three courses. It is also observed (except for unit 10) that the percentage of success in the last units tends to increase slightly, which leads to thinking that little by little the students tend to become more involved in the readings and learning of the material before the explanation in class. Next, the success rate of the students after the theoretical classes is evaluated. In this case, the percentage of correct answers is higher than in the questionnaires before the explanation in class, which implies a high level of student attention during the theoretical sessions. In this case, the percentages of correct answers are between 61% and 95%, with an average of 79.4% in the three courses. Once again, unit 10 stands out with an average correct answer of 85.5%, which implies an increase of 87% concerning the percentage of correct answers before the theory class (the average for the rest of the units is around 26%). This leads to the conclusion that this is a complex topic for students to understand unless they are correctly guided during its development.

Figure 1. Percentage of correct answers in each of the Kahoot! questionnaires conducted in each of the courses analyzed before (BTE) and after (ATE) the explanation of the subject unit.

Figure 2 shows the results of the test conducted on the first day of class to determine the level of student knowledge of the subject. As can be seen at the beginning of the course, knowledge is very low with an average

of 57% of the answers being correct. This is due to the high degree of specialization of the subject, the contents, and the vocabulary used in the port environment. However, the knowledge at the end of the course as observed is much higher with an average of 85% of the questions answered successfully. These good results were also reflected in the final grade of the course, which increased by 1.8 points concerning previous courses in which the usual methodology was used.

Figure 2. Results of the initial test conducted on the first day and the last day of class.

The analysis of the four final questions to determine the degree of student acceptance of the Kahoot! platform (Figure 3) shows that in general, 89% of students consider this learning system to be innovative, fun and motivating in the classroom. The 2020-2021 course is the one that least values the platform as learning dynamize with 79% compared to 85% in 2018-2019 and 2019-2020. Analyzing the questions individually, it is observed that 87% of the students consider that it is a fun way of learning, highlighting the course 2019-2020 with 91%. Interestingly, the same percentage (87%) of students consider that they have learned using this methodology and that they would recommend it. The percentage of 2020-2021 stands out with only 81% in the question on whether they have learned something, while the 2018-2019 and 2019-2020 courses present 93% and 88%, respectively. Finally, concerning the question of the level of satisfaction with the methodology, only 79% of the students said that they had a positive feeling. The 2018-2019 and 2019-2020 academic years stand out again with 73% and 71%, respectively, while the 2020-2021 academic year shows the lowest percentage with only 63%.

Figure 3. Responses to the questions to determine the degree of acceptance of the use of the Kahoot! platform for each of the implementation courses.

4 Discussion

Several studies have shown that the performance of students in class increases at the same time that their motivation increases (Ausó-Monreal et al., 2020; Sousa, 2016). This seems to be in line with the results obtained for two reasons: i) the final grade of the courses in which Kahoot is applied as a dynamic tool increases considerably concerning the courses in which it is not used, and; ii) the success rate of the students in the different questionnaires increases throughout the sessions (Figure 1). The subject of Management and Operation of Ports is within the subjects of transport and urban services so that, in general, students do not show a great interest in this subject (outside the usual scope of this branch), which can be deduced from the low average grade obtained. However, in the years in which the methodology of using the Kahoot platform has been implemented, the average grade has increased by about two points.

The motivation of the student cannot be based solely on the teaching methodology, but the teaching staff plays a very important role (Fernández, 2002; Torelló, 2011). For example, the students in the last course where Kahoot is applied (2020-2021) have the worst opinion of the platform of the three courses analyzed (Figure 3), and yet they are the ones with the highest average grade of the eight courses studied. Nevertheless, this group of students considers that the platform helps them in learning (Figure 3), which is consistent with the results obtained in other similar studies (Ausó-Monreal et al., 2020; Rodríguez-Fernández, 2017). The difficulty of the subject matter can also influence student motivation. Thus, in general, the students can understand and assimilate about 60% of the subject by themselves, while a dynamic and enjoyable explanation by the teacher makes the percentage of success reach almost 80%. In addition, in unit 10, the explanation provided by the teacher increases the percentage of correct answers from 45.7% to 85.5% (Figure 1). Curiously, the success rate in the test on the first day of class (57%, Figure 2) is approximately the same as the final average grade achieved by the students when the Kahoot! platform was not used in teaching.

Another factor that, according to different authors, can affect the degree of attention is the moment in which the subject is taught, such as the day or time of the session (Blake, 1967). In this sense, it can be affirmed that this factor has not influenced the results obtained since the beginning of the course, which has been taught on Wednesdays from three to six o'clock. Finally, to correctly evaluate the real attention level of the students in the program, it would be necessary to conduct the questionnaires every fifteen minutes, because as indicated (among others) by Sousa (2016) throughout the duration of a class, the attention of the student varies, being on average about 15-20 minutes (Bunce et al., 2010). However, this is not feasible given that the length of the units and the organization of the subject do not allow this time to be wasted throughout the class.

5 Conclusion

With all the results obtained in this work, it can be concluded that:

- The flipped classroom allows students to achieve a success rate of about 60% (BTE test), approximately equal to the final grade obtained by students without Kahoot!
- The explanation of the subject matter by the teacher and the use of Kahoot! increases the success rate to 80% (ATE test).
- Student motivation increases throughout the course when using Kahoot!, as demonstrated by the increase in the success rate.
- Some units cannot be understood by the students on their own, and the explanation of the concepts by the teacher is necessary for their correct assimilation.
- In general, students consider that the use of the platform is fun, increases their level of learning and would recommend its use.

To continue increasing the use of the platform, it is necessary to conduct a study on the response time, since some of the students indicated that, although the recreational part motivated them to study the subject, the pressure of having little time to answer the questions made them nervous and stressed them out.

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